
83. The Andromeda photometric survey

THE ANDROMEDA GALAXY, M31, is a large barred spiral galaxy, visible to the naked eye under dark conditions. With a diameter of 65–70 kpc, and at a distance of around 780 kpc, it is the nearest large galaxy to our own (and of similar mass), and indeed the largest member of the Local Group of galaxies.

The formation and subsequent evolution of M31 has been pieced together from various lines of evidence, including its star formation history (Davidge et al., 2012). Current understanding is that it was formed roughly 10 billion years ago from the collision and subsequent merger of smaller protogalaxies, resulting in a high rate of star formation, and most of the galaxy's halo and extended disk. A subsequent close passage with the Triangulum Galaxy (M33) 2–4 billion years ago resulted in further bursts of star formation across its disk, and also in disturbances in the outer disk of M33.

Other interactions with satellite galaxies, perhaps M32 or M110, resulted in its metal-rich giant stellar stream (Ibata et al., 2001). And a merger 100 Myr ago may have created the counter-rotating gas disk in its centre, as well as a relatively young stellar component.

SPECTROSCOPIC STUDIES have provided detailed measurements of the rotational velocity as a function of radial distance from its centre. Its spiral arms, punctuated by a series of H II regions, are tightly wound, although more widely spaced than in our own galaxy.

Of its other major components, Andromeda hosts a dense compact star cluster at its centre, containing a black hole of $1 - 2 \times 10^8 M_{\odot}$. Its extended halo appears to be roughly comparable to our own, with stars being generally metal-poor, and increasingly so with distance.

VARIOUS TECHNIQUES have been used to estimate its distance, including the use of Cepheid variables, an eclipsing binary, and stars at the tip of the red giant branch. With a reasonable agreement amongst them, they yield a distance of 778 ± 34 kpc. Corresponding to a parallax of ~ 1.3 micro-arcsec, this is well beyond reach of Gaia's individual star measurements.

Andromeda seen with (top to bottom): NASA's GALEX (optical); NASA's Spitzer at $24 \mu\text{m}$ (JPL–Caltech/K. Gordon, Univ. Arizona); GALEX (ultraviolet). Bottom: star counts in the centre of the 5° -radius field, on a log scale, from Gaia DR3 (Evans et al., 2022).

THE RELEASE of progressively better Gaia catalogues at roughly 2-year intervals is driven by the increasing quantity of satellite data with time, along with numerous iterative aspects of the data treatment. It means that the scientific community does not have to wait for the final data products. And it also means that user experiences, and any identified shortcomings of an instrumental, calibration, or data treatment nature, can be fed back to ensure appropriate improvements in future releases.

In the first data release (DR1, 2016), *G*-band ‘epoch photometry’ (i.e. the time-series photometry) was made available for 3194 variable stars. In the second data release (DR2, 2018), this number increased to half a million variable stars. With the third data release (DR3, June 2022) about 10 million variables are being made available, along with their time series (Eyer et al., 2022; Rimoldini et al., 2022). The present plans of the Gaia Data Processing and Analysis Consortium are to issue the epoch photometry for all stars with the fourth data release, DR4, around 2025.

A specific initiative to encourage user experience and feedback on these plans for epoch photometry is the Gaia Andromeda Photometric Survey, GAPS, made available as part of the Gaia DR3 data release (Evans et al., 2022). It provides epoch photometry for all sources, variable and constant, from a limited region of the sky.

Amongst the fields considered for this specific initiative were the Ursa Minor dwarf spheroidal galaxy, the intermediate-age open cluster NGC 2516, the Kepler exoplanet field, and the PLATO long-duration fields.

The final choice for this specific data release was largely determined by the satellite scanning law: Andromeda is in a region where the number of scans varies significantly (the 10th and 90th percentiles ranging from 10 to 57 observations). It also encompasses regions of very different star densities, allowing the effects of crowding to be assessed. And with a radius of 5.5 degrees centred on M31, the chosen field includes many Milky Way stars, resulting in a Hertzsprung–Russell diagram where all sequences are well populated.

THE RESULTING data set contains epoch photometry in *G*, *B_p* and *R_p* for 1 257 319 sources, of which the majority have between 30–45 observations. Due to the particular geometry of the scanning law over the 34-month data collection interval of DR3, some 15% have more than 50 observations. In contrast, the central region of M31 has much fewer observations due to crowding (due to the presence of multiple sources in the CCD window for the *G*-band observations, and to the larger overlapping windows in *B_p* and *R_p*). Improvements in both aspects are expected in future data releases.

In terms of star colour (Evans et al., 2022; Figure 9) the field average away from M31 is $B_p - R_p \sim 1.4$, whereas in its spiral arms the average colour is ~ 1.0 .

THE SIMULTANEOUS OBSERVATION in three passbands provides an important means for detecting variability. Evans et al. (2022) describe their use of the variability index, *R*, which characterises the residuals, compared to the mean, in the three passbands (*G*, *B_p* and *R_p*) by means of a *principal component analysis*.

Their Hertzsprung–Russell diagram colour-coded with this *R* variability index provides a convenient way to visualise the location of all types of variable star. Although in the diagram shown here (their Figure 19), the restriction to stars with better than a 10% parallax error means that they are unlikely to be part of M31 itself (note also that the diagram shows mean values in a given area, rather than individual points).

Many of these variables, but not all, have also been identified as part of the variability processing for Gaia DR3 (Eyer et al., 2022; Rimoldini et al., 2022).

MEANWHILE, Evans et al. (2022) have classified the most prominent variability regions, as designated in the figure, as follows:

1. The seven highly variable blue objects below the main sequence are cataclysmic variables.
2. The classical instability strip on the main sequence is formed by δ Scuti stars (p-mode pulsators), along with γ Doradus stars (g-mode pulsators) at lower luminosity.
3. The clump with strong variability at the edge of the giant branch are RS Can Ven-type variables.
4. The very red giants are long-period variables; they include Mira variables, semi-regular variables, and OSARGs (OGLE small amplitude red giants).
5. The faint ridge in the middle of main sequence seems to have been unexpected. A similar feature was present in the diagram of Eyer et al. (2019; Fig. 8).
6. The ridge at the top of the main sequence comprises different variable types, many linked with binaries.

MORE IN-DEPTH analyses of the Gaia variables, and further consideration of many other aspects of the Andromeda Galaxy as seen by Gaia, remain substantial tasks for the future.